

Sediment Dispersion and Siltation Characteristics in the Bay of Bengal

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Department of Geography and Environment

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Sediment Dispersion and Siltation Characteristics in the Bay of Bengal

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Candidate's Declaration

It is hereby declared that this thesis or any part of it has not been submitted elsewhere for the award of any degree or copied from any other work.

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Abbreviations

BARC	Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council
BIWTA	Bangladesh Internal Water Transport Authority
BMD	Bangladesh Meteorological Department
Cms	Centimeters
CZPo	Coastal Zone Policy
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DN	Digital Number
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EMR	Electromagnetic Radiation
eq	Equation
ETM+	Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus
GBM	Ganges Brahmaputra Meghna
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HT	High Tide Level
Kyr	Killoyear
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MSL	Mean Sea Level
MSL	Mean Sea Level

NASA	National Aeronotical and Space Administration
NDSSI	Normalized Difference Suspended Sediment
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NEI	Netherlands Economic Institute
NOAA	National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Association
PG	Projected Gain
PL	Projected Loss
SSC	Suspended Sediment Concentration
SSS	Sea Surface Salinity
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
TM	Thematic Mapper
TOA	Top of Atmospheric
USGS	United States of Geological Survey
Yr	Year

Abstract

Coastal erosion and deposition are currently considered as critical problem for coastal zone management. Suspended sediment is one of significant factors related to cause of erosion and deposition on coastal zone. Hence, monitoring and understanding the suspended sediments dynamics are vital components to handle along coastal problems. Worldwide numerous studies have been conducted on the Suspended Sediment Dispersion and Concentration. In the continental shelf of Bangladesh region, a very few studies were conducted. This study is conducted in the Bangladesh coast of Bay of Bengal. For better understanding about the pattern of suspended sediment distribution and its movement, three types of experiment were done. Firstly, the in-situ data was collected from two study area and these were analyzed in the laboratory. As satellite imagery has been found that can be useful for providing information on coastal study such as offshore circulation and suspended sediments concentration, the second experiment was done to calibrate the in-situ information to the satellite imagery for getting out the spatial distribution of suspended sediment concentration over the whole coastal zone of northern part of the continental shelf. The third experiment was done for understanding the depositional rate of suspended sediment over the continental shelf. It was also included the bottom topography change of the shelf over the last twenty seven years (1982-2007 AD) and projected to the future forty three years (2007-2050AD) which involved the mapping out of the areas of deposition and scouring. Maximum Suspended Sediment is found near the Meghna estuary about 1.9gm/l and minimum found in front of the head of Swatch of No Ground about 0.24 gm/l.

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1. Introduction

Very small particles of soil that remains suspended in water for a considerable period of time are called suspended sediments. These are mainly the eroded materials washed from the catchment area and under the favorable condition of fluvial transportation these are mixed with running water and are being carried to the large water body where the running water losses its velocity to transport them. These suspended sediments are mainly consisted of fine sands, silts and clay particles. As they are very small, they can be easily transported by the running water. Suspended sediments are very important for deltaic country like Bangladesh because they play critical role in the formation of new lands or islands and in the changing of shoreline configuration and local tide level. In coastal zone management, coastal dam building and navigation work, it is very important to identify the amount and movement of suspended sediments and their distribution pattern. Suspended sediment concentration (SSC) and their dispersal are very important parameter in the study of coastal areas, catchments and river mouths. SSC is the amount of suspended sediment found per liter of water and dispersal of SSC indicates their spatial distribution in water body. In this research three levels of study is done for better understanding about the suspended sediment concentration and its dispersal pattern on the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal of Bangladesh region. Firstly, Suspended sediment concentration was estimated from field data. Secondly, field data was correlated with remotely sensed satellite imagery for carrying out spatial pattern of SSC distribution over the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal of Bangladesh region and thirdly, bathymetric analysis was done for the last 27 years (1982-2009) in order to identify the areas of sedimentation and scouring with the rate of sedimentation and scouring. The results were predicted up to 2025 and 2050 for locating potential land emergence areas over the continental shelf.

1.2. Background

Many works on suspended sediment dispersion have been done worldwide. Harris, *et.al.* (2008) studied about suspended sediment on the northwestern Adriatic Sea which was very mathematical and used ROMS. In that study they used water discharge and prevailing wind pattern as the controlling factor of SSC distribution. But they did not

considered salinity that is a dominant factor for spatial distribution of SSC. Likely, some research was done on the Indian coast of Bay of Bengal. But in Bangladesh, very few attempts have been done on the estimation of suspended sediment concentration and their dispersal pattern over the continental shelf region of Bangladesh in Bay of Bengal. Some works were done by several researchers like Kuehl, et.al. (1989), Barua (1990) and Curry, et.al.(1971) in the Bay of Bengal. But these were mostly based on geological perspective and hardly concerned with the spatial distribution of suspended sediment. Islam, et.al. (2001) conducted a research at the Ganges–Brahmaputra River mouth and estimated the suspended sediment concentration. It is considered as the primary work in the estimation of SSC in the coastal sea of Ganges–Brahmaputra River mouth that was mainly based on remote sensing image analysis and did not concern with ground data. But for accurate estimation, remote sensing process highly recommends satellite data to calibrate with ground data. In this present study, remote-sensing data, filed data and bathymetric data were used for the better understanding of suspend sediment concentration and its dispersal characteristics as well as the siltation characteristics along the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal in Bangladesh region.

1.3. Objective

The main focus of the research will be to understand “the sediment dispersion over the continental shelf in Bay of Bengal”. Accordingly, the following specific objectives have been set for the study:

- (i) Estimation of the suspended sediment concentration.
- (ii) Identifying the spatial distribution of suspended sediment concentration.
- (iii) Identifying the major factors controlling their spatial distribution.
- (iv) Estimation of the rate of sediment deposition on the continental shelf.
- (v) Understanding the bottom topography change of the continental shelf.
- (vi) Mapping out the depositional and scouring area on the continental shelf over the last 27 years (1982-2007) and
- (vii) Calculation of the volume of erosional and depositional sediment during that period.

The outcome of the study will provide a picture about the sediment dispersion and associated change of the floor of continental shelf over the Bay of Bengal that may be helpful for coastal zone management of the country.

1.4. Methodology

The methodology of this research work can be divided into three categories, such as the conceptual development activities, methods of data collection and data analysis.

Conceptual Development Stage

The beginning of every research work is started with the procedures of conceptual development. Theoretical framework about any research depends on these procedures. In this beginning stage, related literatures are surveyed. It is including the review of relevant books, articles, journals, reports, papers and dissertations of both published and unpublished. It helps to understand the background of the work and introduces about different methods and techniques that can be used in the research to reach the specific goal. Learning about the Remote Sensing data acquisition technique, operational interfaces of different geo-statistical software, 3D model making software are also included in this stage.

Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data are used in this research. Primary Data were collected directly from the field and secondary data were collected from navigation chart that are used for the analysis of the bottom topography of Bay of Bengal. Overall collected data and their sources are given in Table 1. The detail procedure of bottom topography analysis is described in the chapter-5.

Field work

When the concept about the research becomes clear the next stage comes in front and this is the field work. It is started with the selection of the study site. This stage is included the selection of sample size, base map preparation, sample collection instrument making and gathering all necessary utensils that will be necessary in the field. First of all, the suspended sediment zone along the coastal belt of Bangladesh was demarcated from the satellite imagery (Landsat 7 ETM+). Considering the time

and financial constraint careful decision was taken in the selection of the two study sites; 3 kilometers south in the Bay of Bengal from the Nijhum Dwip and the Kuakata sea beach. It was decided to collect samples from the five points for each study site. The base maps were prepared based on the Google Earth image taken from 500m eye altitude that was geographically referenced using the WGS-1984 projection system.

Figure 1: Complete Illustration of Research Methodology

The base maps were gridded into a number of squared grids in order to select the sample points in the study sites. In the field we used Trahler¹ for collection samples from the selected points. We selected the points in the field by a hand GPS (Magellan version) and with the help of water sampler the water samples were collected from three different layers of water column; surface, bottom and middle of surface and bottom layer from each sample point. With an alcoholic thermometer in situ water temperature was recorded for each sample. The pH was recorded using the pH meter. Every sample were given specific number and brought to the laboratory for analysis.

Table 1: Collected Data and Their Sources

Data Type	Description of Data	Data Source
Primary	Water sample collection	Field work
	In situ temperature data	
	In situ pH data	
Secondary	Navigation data	Bangladesh NAVY
	Satellite Imagery	USGS/Earth Explorer
	Tidal data	BIWTA
	Salinity data	BIWTA,NASA
	Temperature data	BMD,NOAA
	Surface Current data	Admiralty chart of Bay of Bengal
	Wave Data	Secondary literature

¹ A little boat, that is driven by a shallow engine and is particularly used by the fisherman for fishing in the coastal region of the Bay of Bengal.

Data analysis

This stage was started with data preparation in the laboratory from the collected samples. The water samples were filtered using filter paper to obtain the sediment concentration (gm/l) that was suspended in water. Particle density was measured using the psychomotor method. The navigation data (bathymetry) was carefully analyzed using Arc-GIS, Micro-Dem, 3-dem and Surfer v10 software packages. For remote sensing data analysis, satellite images were processed and analyzed using the ERDAS-IMAGINE-10. Detail procedure of remote sensing data processing and analysis is described in the chapter-4. Excel spreadsheet-2007 was used to create graphs and tables. Overall methodology is illustrated in Figure 1.

1.5. Coastal Belt of Bangladesh

Coastal belt demarcation of any country is not very easy because of their varying geometric and physiographic characteristics. Conflicting maritime and political boundaries, area of EEZ and continental shelf are also other major criteria that must be considered while demarcating actual coastal belt of any coastal country. Several attempts have been made to define coastal belt where different criteria have been used such as, tidal influence, physiographic and geomorphic characteristics of the coast, extent of marine biology, salinity influence etc. But none of these could provide a clear concept about the delimitation of actual coastal belt of a country. However, the Coastal Zone Policy (CZPo, 2005) of the Government of Bangladesh declared 19 districts out of 64 are in the coastal zone covering a total of 147 upazillas of the country of which 12 are grouped under the exposed zone (Figure 2). According to Pramanik (1983) the coastal belt of Bangladesh can be divided into three distinctive regions as the western, central, eastern coast based on coastal configuration, geomorphologic features, topographic settings and hydrodynamic characteristics (Figure 2). Accordingly, the length of coastal belt is about 710 km (Snead, 1985) extending from the southwestern end of Khulna district in the west to Bodormokam, the southern tip of Teknaf peninsula. But the total shoreline of Bangladesh would be thousands of kilometers long if the length of the tidal- estuarine coast is considered.

Figure 2: Location of Two Study Areas along the Coastal Belt of Bangladesh

Source: Shape file of Bangladesh from BARC (2004) and Bathymetric contour lines from <http://geocommons.com/overlays/4390>

While considering the 3m contour line as the northern limit of the coastal belt then the area would be about one quarter of the national territory (Broadus, 1993). However, along this coastal belt the western coast is extended from the southern end of the Sundarbans in the Bangladesh territory up to the eastern corner of Sundarban covering the Satkhira, Khulna, Bagerhat, Pirojpur, Barguna and Patuakhali districts. The central zone is extended from the eastern corner of the Patuakhali district to the Feni river estuary covering Noakhali, Barisal, Bhola, Laxmipur and Feni districts and the eastern coast is started from Bodormokam, the southern tip of mainland to the Feni river estuary. The western coast lies at 0.9 to 2.1 meter above mean sea level which is under the threat of subsidence due to weak fluvial process. In the eastern zone sediment supply is also low only comes from the nearby hills. But the central zone is very dynamic. Fluvial process is very active in this region due to huge supply of water and sediment through the GBM river system from Himalaya and adjacent catchment

areas. The sediments are dispersed in the estuary and due to flow velocity, current, wind and tidal influence these are distributed at different magnitudes over the continental shelf. The primary motive of this study is to understand the distribution pattern of suspended sediment over the continental shelf of Bangladesh.

1.6. Significance of the Study

Suspended sediment is one of the significant parameter of water and a good indicator of coastal erosion and water quality monitoring. It captures deep attention when it plays a critical role in the formation of new lands and in the change of shoreline configuration of a deltaic country like Bangladesh. But during coastal zone management, navigation path selection char land development and artificial dam building this vital parameter and its dispersion pattern is not considered. In this circumstance it becomes very essential to know about the spatial distribution of suspended sediment concentration and the factors that are responsible in its dispersion. It will help in efficient coastal zone management, deep sea port establishment, navigation route selection and demarcation of countries coastal zone. This study is a little effort that will help to understand the dispersal pattern of suspended sediment over the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal of Bangladesh part.

Chapter Two: Study Area- The Bay of Bengal

2.1. Introduction

Bay of Bengal is the northeastern extending arm of the Indian Ocean, located between peninsular India and Burma. It occupies an area about 2,200,000 sq. km with an average water depth of 2586 meter (Das, 1998) with a maximum depth of 5,258 meter and is bordered on the north by the Ganges and Brahmaputra River delta, on the east by the Burmese peninsula and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, on the west by India and eastern coast of Sri-Lanka, and on the south along the line drawn between from Dondra Head in the south of Sri-Lanka and northern tip of Sumatra.. It is triangle shaped with an absolute location 5°N to 22°N latitude and 80°E to 100°E longitude.

2.2. Topographic Characteristics

The Bottom topography of the Bay of Bengal is almost U shaped with a thick abyssal plain. This abyssal plain occupies almost the entire part of the Bay of Bengal with gently sloping towards the south at an angle of 8° to 10° (Islam, 2001). The underwater valley is dissected in many places by this plain mass. Major topographic features are the Continental shelf, Swath of no ground, Sunda Trench, Ninety East Ridge, Eighty-five Ridge and Bengal Fan (Figure 3).

The Continental Shelf borders the Bay of Bengal towards the east, north and west with its varying slope and width and thickness. The shelf is wider towards the north and becomes narrower as it reaches towards the south. The width is maximum along the Bangladesh coast about 160km and minimum along the east coast of Sri-Lanka which is about 5 to 25 km. Along the Bangladesh coast the shelf is gently sloping with an average slope of 1:800 that is about 45° along the eastern coast of Sri-Lanka. There is a debate about the outer limit of the shelf. The 100 fathom isobaths (180 meter) is considered as the outer limit of the shelf (Islam(2001) whereas Kuehl *et. al.* (1989) suggested 80 meter depth as the outer limit. Considering the depth of 100 fathom, the area of the continental shelf under Bangladesh covers 4100 km² (Islam, 1975).

Figure 3: Features of Bottom Topography in Bay of Bengal. The barbed line indicates the edge of continental shelf, dashed lines are the isobaths and the dropped lines indicate the outer boundary of most active sub fan.

Source: Regenerated from Curry et al. (2003)

The Swatch of No Ground is also another significant feature in the Bay of Bengal that is a submarine canyon with 5 to 7 km wide floor and about 12° inclined wall. It is

situated at the head of the Bay of Bengal that is only 25 km south from the Bangladesh coastline. It cuts the continental shelf diagonally and has a sea ward continuation about 2000km into the Bay of Bengal. At the edge of the shelf, depths in the trough are about 1,200m. This submarine canyon is also known as the Ganga Trough. The sandbars and ridges near the mouth of the Ganges Brahmaputra delta pointing toward the Swatch of no Ground showing sediments are tunneled through this trough into the deeper part of the Bay of Bengal. It is feeding the Bengal Deep Sea Fan by turbidity currents. There is debate about the origination of this canyon. Dietz (1955) suggested that the canyon was formed by the turbidity current originating at the head of the bay. According to Shepard (1973), canyons are cut sub aerially during the Pleistocene low sea level where turbidity current played the significant role in the process. According to Chowdhury (1959) the Swatch of no ground is the left feature on the estuary during the post glacial sea-level rise as the coastline gradually shifted towards the north. The canyon itself is 20–30 km wide, with steep walls ($> 10^\circ$) on its eastern side and shallower slopes ($\sim 5^\circ$) on the western wall. Both of the walls of the canyon are dissected by gullies, which apparently constitute a network for sediment transport into the canyon (Kuehl *et. al.* 1989; Kuehl *et. al.* 1997; Kottke *et. al.* 2003). However, this submarine canyon plays a significant role on the tidal activities and coastal process along the continental shelf of Bangladesh.

Sunda Trench also known as Java Trench is another submarine feature in the Bay of Bengal that is running parallel along the west side of the arc of the Nicobar and Andaman islands and extending northward up to 10°N into the Bay and joins the eastern limit of the Himalayan range. It is tectonically in origin at the junction of the Indian and Myanmar plates.

Ninety East Ridge is another major feature that is situated in the Indian Ocean and runs in a north-south direction approximately along the longitude 90°E . It is a submarine mountain range about 5000kms long that is extended from 30° south to 15° north latitude. It lies at the immediate outboard of the Sunda Trench between the Bengal Fan and the Nicobar Fan. This ridge has been the site of active sea floor spreading. During the cretaceous period the Bengal basin was originate as a rift valley

on the crest of the Ninety East Ridge. Due to the spreading on the ridge axis the valley was continuously widened and took the funnel shaped bay. With the opening of the Bay, a number of transformed fault have been developed and the ridge began to grow wider with the deposition of sediment along the rift valley.

Eighty-Five Ridge is another ridge in the Bay of Bengal that is located along 85°E longitude. It was identified by Curry *et.al.* (1982) based on seismic record More than 5 km thick sediments have been deposited on either sides of the ridge. It is appeared to close to the foot of the continental slope (Curry *et.al.*1982) and more than 5kms thick sediment have been deposited on either side of the ridge. The Eighty-five Ridge together with the Ninety-East Ridge constitutes about 7.5 km thickness of sediment.

Bengal Fan is the largest submarine fan of the world. It extends from 20° north to 7° south latitude with an estimated length of 2800 to 3000 km along north-south direction and about 830 to 1430km wide along east-west direction (Curry and Moore, 1974). It has very gentle southward slope with varying thickness of sediment about 5 to 8 km. Most sediment in the fan has been derived from the Himalayas and the average sedimentation rate is 4cm/kyr (Curry and Moore, 1974). Together with its eastern lobe, the Nicobar fan, it covers an area of 3106 sq km. The sediment layer is about 16 km thick beneath the northern Bay of Bengal. Sediments are tunneled to the fan via a delta-front trough, the Swatch of no Ground. Major part of Bengal fan sediment constitutes the Terrigenous sediment that started to deposit in the Eocene age (58 to 37 million years ago) as a response to the first intraplate collision (Curry and Moore, 1971).

2.3. Climatic Characteristics

The climate of the Bengal region varies from tropical to subtropical conditions. The Bay of Bengal is influenced by the wet southwest summer Monsoon and the colder, dryer continental northeast Monsoon during winter. The southwest Monsoon dominates from June through September with southwest maritime winds bringing strong rainfall to most of the area. Monsoon rains and coincident destructive cyclone storms recurrently cause great loss of life along the northern coast. On the average, four to six Monsoon depressions form in the Bay of Bengal during the southwestern

Monsoon season. By early October the southwest Monsoon has almost withdrawn and the dry, continental Monsoon winds from northeasterly directions prevail during November and December.

2.4. Sea Surface Temperature

Surface water temperature of the Bay of Bengal is greatly influenced by the presence of landmass on its three sides. The mean annual temperature of the surface water is about 28°C. The maximum temperature is observed in May (30°C) and the minimum (25°C) in January-February (Das, 1992, 1998). But the annual variation in temperature is not great, about 2°C in the south and 5°C in the north.

Figure 4: Spatial Variation of Sea Surface Temperature in Bay of Bengal. Highest temperature is 32°C and lowest temperature is 28°C for the May month of 2012. Red rectangles indicate the two study areas

Data Source: NOAA, 2012

The temperature also shows a horizontal (Figure 4) and vertical variation (Figure 5). It remains almost same for the upper 50 m water depth and suddenly decreases more

than 10°C up to 200m depth. At 500m depth the average temperature is about 15°C and at 2000m depth it is less than 2°C (Das, 1992).

Figure 5: Vertical Variation of Water Temperature (a) and Salinity (b) in Bay of Bengal. Highest temperature is found within 100m water depth and it decrease suddenly as depth of water increases below 50m. With contrast to temperature, salinity increases with the increasing of depth from the MSL. Maximum salinity (30‰) is obtained after reaching the depth below 100m.

Source: Redrawn from Das, (1992)

2.5. Oceanographic Characteristics

2.5.1. Tide

In Bay of Bengal the tide is mainly semi-diurnal with slight diurnal inequality that involves two high and two low tides during the period of 24 hours and 52 minutes. Where the depth of the shelf is shallow particularly in the estuary the tidal range becomes highest (Figure 6). In the extensive shallow areas in the north-eastern corner of the bay, the tidal range increases due to partial reflection. The tide along Bangladesh coast originating from the Indian Ocean enter into the continental shelf through the two submarine canyons and reaches Cox's Bazar and Hiron point at the same time. These two points are being practically at the heads of submarine canyons

i.e. swatch of no ground and Burma trench. The ranges of the tides at the tip of these two canyons i.e. Hiron point and Cox's Bazar being about, 10 feet during the spring tides of the equinoxes.

Figure 6: Average Tidal Range of Central and Eastern Coast Of Bangladesh Part in Bay of Bengal. 2001, 2002 and 2003 are indication of three different years of which the tidal data are used here. Except the Saflapur station the high tide range is significantly decreased in other two stations. From careful analysis it is seen that in Hatia station the low tide limit has been decreased to less than -0.5m whereas in other two stations it has been increased during the period of 2001-2008.

Data Source: BIWTA

2.5.2. Wave

The wave generated in the Bay is highly influenced by the seasonal wind pattern, seasonal current pattern and tidal fluctuation. In the deep sea the waves are large in their wavelengths and as they reach towards the continental they break and the height becomes high with decreasing wave length. The wave breaks mainly occurred due to the shallow continental shelf.

Figure 7: Bottom sediment re-suspension mechanism induced by wave.

Source: Modified after Bird, 2008(2nd ed)

In the Meghna estuary the heights of the waves become highest. In the monsoon season the heights of waves near the shore reaches more than 1.5 meter, but in the pre-monsoon and in the post monsoon period the height remains less than 1.5 meter. Wave observations using a wave rider buoy at the Sandwip Channel, off the Karnofully River mouth in 1977, (from January to mid August) show only a moderate wave climate with a maximum wave height of only 2.4 m. The average of the significant wave height during these two months is less than 1 m. The wave periods varied from 3.5 s for a 0.5 m wave to 6 s for a 2 m wave (NEI, 1978). Data compiled by the U.S. Navy (Barua and Kana, 1995) for the Bay of Bengal shows that high seas (wave height > 2.5 m) and high swells (swell height > 3.8 m) occur only 1% of the observed time during the northeast monsoon; the frequencies change to 9% and 16%, respectively, during the southwest monsoon. The periods from November to February are dominated by calm conditions. Wave plays a significant role in the re-suspension of bottom sediment in the water (Figure 7). It also acts as an agent for the movement of sediment load and long shore drifting process.

2.5.3. Sea Level

Sea Level due to the influence of water density and wind the seasonal changes of the sea level in the Bay are remarkable and one of the highest in the world. Due to the funnel shaped geometry of the Bay, the maximum seasonal variation is observed along the north-east coast. On the east coast of India the annual change is 50 cm whereas along the Chittagong coast it is 118cm (Das, 1992).The range at Khidirpur is 166 cm, at Kolkata.

2.5.4. Current

The surface circulation in Bay of Bengal is seasonal and changes its direction and rate considerably during the courses of the year. It is found to be generally clockwise from January to July and counter-clockwise from August to December, in accordance with the reversible monsoon wind systems. The flow is not constant and depends on the strength and duration of the winds.

Figure 8: Seasonal Current Pattern over the Bay of Bengal. a-January, b-July and c-November. (Mean rate (knots) is indicated in above figures for rates of $\frac{1}{4}$ knot or more. The constancy of a current is indicated by different color of arrow.)

Source of a, b and c: Bangladesh Admiralty Chart, 1978

During the summer monsoon, the general movement of water is eastward in the open sea, which being deflected right due to coriolis force ²and turned into clockwise ocean circulation with average current of 0.5 knot/hour. But during the winter monsoon, when the current in open sea is westward, it is anticlockwise within the bay (Islam, 2001) (Figure 8). In January, the north-east current is well established which develop a westward flow across most part of the Bay. At 15° north, the current bifurcates near the Indian coast. The northern branch of the current moves clockwise forming a gyre along the Orissa coast, where the current becomes highest which is about 1 knot/hour during February. This gyre gradually become weaker but occupies most part of the Bay. In May the gyre nearly disappear and there remains a general north-east or east current across most part of the Bay and south-west current along the east coast of India which finally meet the Sumatra current.

2.5.5. Salinity

The surface salinity of the Bay of Bengal is highly influenced by the surface current and fresh water input from rivers and their numerous distributaries. It varies place to place due to the variation of fresh water input and also month to month (Figure 9). The surface salinity in the open part of the Bay oscillates from 32‰ to 34.5‰ and in the coastal region varies from 10‰ to 25‰. But at the river mouths, the surface salinity decreases to 5‰ or even less. The coastal water is significantly diluted throughout the year, although the river water is greatly reduced during winter. Along the coast of the Ganges-Brahmaputra Delta, salinity decreases to 1‰ during summer and increases up to 15‰ to 20‰ in winter. Salinity gradually increases from the coast towards the open part of the Bay. The surface salinity at the mouths of large rivers like the Ganges, Brahmaputra and Meghna River system varies widely from one day to another, especially in summer. Salinity of water also changes vertically. The influence of the fresh water is experienced up to depths of 200-300m. From the

²An weather patterns and legendary cause of the direction the water swirls down the sink. The main cause of the Coriolis Effect is the earth's rotation. As the earth spins in a counter-clockwise direction on its axis anything flying or flowing over a long distance above moves freely its surface is deflected. This occurs because as something above the earth's surface, the earth is moving east under the object at a faster speed.

surface, the salinity gradually increases downward and at about 200-300m it reaches 35‰ and at about 500m the salinity is more than 35.10‰, but at 1,000m it decreases slightly and attains 34.95‰ (Figure 10). With further increase of depth salinity decreases and at 4,500m it is close to 34.7‰ (Rahman, 2007).

Figure 9: Month Salinity Fluctuation in Bay of Bengal

Data Source: NASA (2008), Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology

Figure 10: Vertical Change of Salinity in the Bay of Bengal

Data Source: NASA(2009), Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology

2.6. Sedimentation Characteristics

Siltation is one of the most striking oceanographic features of the northern Bay of Bengal. Sedimentary processes may, in fact, influence the estuarine and near shore fishery ecology of the waters of Bangladesh. Denudation of the Himalaya has resulted in the formation of the world's largest delta which is still active, growing at a rate of about seventy cms every thousand years (Curry and Moore, 1971; Biswash, 1978). The Ganges-Brahmaputra river system brings this sediment down and drains it into the Bay of Bengal. The Meghna system seems to filter the sediment while passing through the depressions (haors) of the Sylhet basin and, therefore, contributes less to the process. A total of six million m^3/s of water carrying an estimated 2,179 million t of sediment is carried down to the sea each year by the Ganges-Brahmaputra river system (Curay and Moore, 1971). Other major sources of siltation in the region are due to the increased run-off during the rainy season as well as floods and the increased erosion of topsoil as a result of coastal inland vegetation depletion. Massive

earthworks in coastal development projects and possibly also rapid horizontal expansion of other land-use practices (e.g. aquaculture), affect the natural siltation process of the inshore and estuarine habitats.

The accretion-erosion process of islands like Hatia, Sandwip and Bhola indicate a strong sedimentary process in the vast Ganges-Brahamaputra-Meghna estuary, which constitutes about 12,800 km² of in-shore fish habitat. Sandwip has lost over 72 km² between 1953 and 1982, as compared to 190 km² in the last two centuries. Hatia, which increased to about 1070 km² from 307 km² between 1779 and 1945, lost 700 km² of accreted land by 1979. Huge rates of accretion in the past indicate an extensive amount of deposit carried down by the rivers; likewise, increased erosion in recent years must be translated in terms of heightened sediment transfers out to sea.

2.7. Sample Location

For understanding the sediment dispersion pattern, two study sites were primarily selected based on the sediment input in the Bay. Lower Meghna River and the Tentulia Channel are two major rivers that are feeding the Bay with sediment and fresh water. Considering this, the Nijhum Dwip and the Kuakata beach were selected as study site for collection of water samples. Fluvial and oceanographic characteristics of these two study sites are broadly described below.

2.8. Site 01: Nijhum Dwip

Nijhum Dwip is a small island covering an area of 77.73 km² (BBS, 1992) situated at the southern peak of the Hatia upazila under Noakhali district. It is a recently discovered island 2 kilometers southwest of Hatia and bounded by Hatia mainland in the north, Meghna River in the east and west and Bay of Bengal in the South. It is located in the west of Damar Char and east of Manpura(Figure 11). Its geographical location is 22° 3" North Latitude and 91°0" East Longitude. The island is divided into 2 parts by a Canal – Kamalarpur (Northern part) and Char Osman (Southern Part). It is a Mauza out of 9 Mauzas under Zahajmara Union of Hatia Thana.

Figure 11: Study Site-1(Nijhum Dwip). The numbers confined in the yellow rectangles are indication of the sample points.

Source: Sample points are collected from field survey

It is an unprotected island with 20 kms long sandy and grassy beach. During 1960s it was a small piece of sandy barren land that consists of Kamlar Char and Char Osman. It was not settled until 1970, until then only seasonally. The devastating cyclone of 1970 swept away almost all settlers who were settled covering 253 ha stable land. Afterward it became calm and quite land. Areas partly submerged during monsoon. Because of riverbank erosion in nearby areas, especially Hatiya, Shahbajpur and Ramgati people migrated to the island as new settlers. Subsequently, a substantial afforestation drive was undertaken by the forestry department of Bangladesh. The island soon became a recognised eco-tourist spot because of the perennial mangrove forests and wild life. People of this island have to fight against natural calamity all the year round. In 2001, a significant portion of the island was designated as Nijhum Dwip National Park under the jurisdiction of Noakhali district in Bangladesh.

The population in Nijhum Dwip was 4372 (1991) and 4742 (2000) with a Sex Ratio: 104(BBS, 2001). Their main occupations are cultivation, fishing and livestock farming.

Average temperature is 25-32°C and Salinity varied from 15-25 ppt and 4-12 ppt seasonally. Salinity remains low from February to June. During this period salinity increases during the Low tide and decreases during the high tide. Salinity concentration range between low and high tide limit is nearly 400 ppm (Figure 12). Tidal influence is very active and the coastal water body remains turbid all the year round. Both High tide and Low tide increases from the January to September and starts to decrease from October. In the near shore of Nijhum Dwip tidal fluctuation is 1.3 to 2.5 m during the High tide and -0.4 to -0.8m during the period of Low tide (Figure 13.).

Figure 12: Average Month Salinity during High Tide and Low Tide at Hatia Station.

Source: BIWTA, (2000-2008)

Figure 13: Average Month Tidal Range during High Tide and Low Tide at Hatia Station

Source: BIWTA, (2008)

2.9. Site 02: Kuakata

The Kuakata, a panoramic sea beach on the southernmost tip of Bangladesh, is located in the northern part of Bay of Bengal. It is in Latachapli union under Kalapara Upazila of Patuakhali district and is about 30 km in length and 6 km in breadth. The Geographic location is $21^{\circ} 49'E$ longitude and $90^{\circ}07'N$ latitude (Figure 14). It is 70 km from Patuakhali district headquarters. The long sea beach extends between the Nilgonj river confluence at the west and the dead portion of Gangamati khal confluence at the east. The main part of Kuakata beach is exposed to continuous erosion due to wave action and storm surges (Rahman, 2012). The coast is wider and the beach has a very flat slope. In 23.56 km long shoreline, erosion occurs in 13.59 km reach and deposition occurs in 9.97 km during the period of 1973 to 2010 (Rahman,2012). Maximum width of beach area, which has been eroded, is about 450 m and accreted is about 1075 m during last 37 years. Daily waves are very small, i.e., averaged wave heights are around 1 m. Due to wave action the soil from the root zone is being washed out. Tides in the beach area are semi-diurnal and daily tidal level varies within the range of 1 to 1.5 m. From March to October the wind blows over Kuakata area from south with an average velocity of 3.5 m/s. From November to January the wind blows from the north with an average velocity of 2.6m/s. Average

Figure 14: Study Site-2(Koakata). The numbers confined in the yellow rectangles are indicated the sample points.

Source: Sample points were collected from field survey

salinity of water is high from March to July which is more than 2000ppm during both High Tide and Low Tide (Figure 15). The variation of salinity between High Tide and Low tide is about 1000ppm for the above months. After June salinity decreases significantly and it remains almost same up to the month of January. Average sea surface temperature is 18°-32° C (Source: *BIWTA (2008)*)

Figure 16).The coastal area is experiencing rapid erosion especially at the west part and the natural sandy beach is under threat due to regular wave action.

Figure 15: Average Salinity during High Tide and Low Tide at Khepupara (Patuakhali) Station

Source: BIWTA (2008)

Figure 16: Average Temperature at Khepupara (Patuakhali) Station

Source: BMD (2008)

2.10. Conclusion

The north eastern coast (Bangladesh coast) of Bay of Bengal is identical by its funnel shape. It gets input of fresh water from numerous rivers and their distributaries. Due to funnel shape the tidal fluctuation is comparatively high near shore of the continental shelf. Another major factor of the tidal and wave action is the shallowness

of the continental shelf. As a result, sediments carried by the GBM systems cannot move beyond the 5m contour line. Maximum of this suspended sediments are deposited within the 5m contour line on the continental shelf. During the period of active monsoon, suspended sediments may reach to the 10m contour line. A number of atmospheric disturbance generate during the monsoon in the deep ocean that hit the coast and play a critical role in the distribution of suspended sediment. Seasonal variation of current pattern also contributes significantly in suspended sediment dispersion over the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal.

**Chapter Three: Calculation of Suspended Sediment Concentration
Using Field Data**

3.1. Introduction

Definition of Suspended Sediment Concentration is already discussed in section 1.1. This chapter basically includes the analysis of field data. Here different types of ocean sediment and their sources in relation to Bay of Bengal, distribution pattern of the suspended sediment carried by the river flow and the factors behind their distributions over the continental shelf are broadly analyzed. The horizontal and vertical change of suspended sediment as well as the pH and salinity of the study areas are also illustrated in this chapter.

3.2. Definition and Types of Ocean Sediment

Ocean sediments are basically small insoluble particles of rocks, soil, volcanoes, chemicals and organic bodies, which are delivered into the ocean from lands via rivers, streams and lakes. These particles are of different sizes and volumes, and are commonly present on the shores of oceans as well as under their surface in the form of tiny stones, rock particles and gravels. There are multiple reasons behind the creation and transportation of these sediments into the ocean, ranging from soil erosion (loss) to volcanic eruptions, from earthquakes to wind storms, and from glacial melting to simply the movement of water under or over Earth's surface. Because different sediments have different compositions, some accumulate faster than others, while some are more likely to dissolve in the ocean water.

One of the first comprehensive studies of deep –sea sediments was made by Murry and Renard in 1891. They examined more than 12000 samples, some of which were obtained by the Challenger. They proposed a classification that is still valid today after hundreds of other studies have been made. They proposed two major groups of ocean sediment: pelagic sediments and terrigenous sediments.

Pelagic sediments are found in the deep part of the ocean far from land; they have settled down through the water in the absence of strong currents. They include Biogenous deposits, Inorganic deposits, Authigenic deposits and Volcanic deposits.

Figure 17: World Distribution of Ocean Sediment (Red rectangle is the demarcation area of Bay of Bengal)

Source: Modified after Duxbury et. al. (2005)

Sediments that come from pre existing rocks are commonly called as **terrigenous sediments**. They are produced by an interplay of chemical and physical weathering processes, which collectively serve to create small grains of material ranging in size from thousandths of millimeters to 1 or 2 millimeters (0.04 or 0.08 inch). Continental rocks and particles may be blown from the land by wind, or carried by water or ice, to settle on the seafloor as terrigenous sediment. They include Red clay, terrigenous mud's, Turbidites and Glacial deposits.

After compiling several classification of ocean sediment it can be concluded that there are basically four types of ocean sediments and these are Biogenous, terrigenous, Hydrogenous and Cosmogenous sediment. Terrigenous sediments are described above. Biogenous sediment is produced by marine organisms. This type of sediment includes siliceous ooze and calcareous ooze and is dependent upon the biomass and skeleton formation of organisms inhabiting the water. According to Rachael James (2005), only between one and ten percent of skeletal debris becomes sediment. The rest is dissolved in the ocean water either before reaching the seafloor or shortly afterward. Hydrogenous sediment is created by chemical reactions in seawater to form minerals

that accumulate as sediment. Sediment created by objects from space, such as meteors, is called cosmogenous sediment (Duxbury *et. al.* 2005:114-116). Major sources of ocean sediments are given in Table 2. According to Rachael James (2005:59), close to continental margins where inputs of material from the land are high, terrigenous sediments can accumulate at rates as high as a few meters per thousand years, enough to obliterate any biological component. By contrast, the accumulation rate of siliceous ooze is of the order of a few meters per million years.

Table 2: Sources of Ocean Sediments

Type	Source	Areas of Significant Deposit	Example
Lithogenous	Eroded rock Volcanoes Airborne Dust	Terrigenous Neritic Pelagic	Boulder-Sand Sand-silt Silt-Red clay
Hydrogenous	Chemical Precipitation from Sea Water	Neritic Pelagic	Phosphate Manganese Nodules
Cosmogenous	Outer space	Pelagic	Meteoritos
Biogenous	Living organisms	Terrigenous Neritic Pelagic	Plant matter Coral, Bony remain Oozes Silicious Calcereous

Source: Modified from Duxbury *et. al.* (2005)

In Bay of Bengal sediments are mainly terrigenous type (Duxbury *et. al.* 2005) (Figure 17) on the continental shelf and calcareous type dominate the deep Sea. Sediments are fine seaward and westward with the thickest accumulation of mud near the submarine canyon, the Swatch of no Ground. The zone receives a large volume of discharge from the Ganges-Bhrahmaputra-Meghna river system, forming high volume of silty deposition. More than 70% of the sediment load of the region is silt; with an additional 10% sand. The shallow part (less than 20m) of the continental shelf off the coast of Chattagong and Teknaf is covered by sand and the intertidal areas show well-

developed sandy beaches. The shallower part of southern continental shelf off the coast of the Sundarbans, Patuakhali and Noakhali is covered by silt and clay; and extensive muddy tidal flats are developed along the shoreline. Some of the shoals and sand ridges present on this part of the continental shelf show an elongation pattern pointed towards the Swatch of no Ground.

3.3. Factors Affecting Sediments in Suspension

Size of suspended sediment, their dispersion and concentration and how long period of time they will remain in the suspension are controlled by several fluvial and oceanographic factors. Among these Water discharge, Ocean wave and tide, Ocean current, sea surface temperature and water salinity are great important. These are described below.

3.3.1. Ocean Wave and Tide

Wave: Wave is surface oscillation of ocean water without changing position but movement of energy. Wind generated waves are surface waves that occur on the free surface of fluid. Waves in the oceans can travel thousands of miles before reaching land. Wind waves range in size from small ripples to huge waves over 30 meters high. These wind generated waves in the ocean are called ocean surface waves. Besides wind activity, Waves can be generated due to Tsunami and Earthquake along the fault line on the ocean floor. In general Tsunami and earthquake induced waves become very destructive with their high magnitude and energy. In Bay of Bengal waves are mainly generated in the Indian Ocean part and reaches to the continental shelf. In the deep sea, wave heights are comparatively low with their long wave length but as they reach to the shallow and irregular bottom topography of continental shelf wave length decreases and the height increase due to wave diffraction. Wave activity is very high in the central coast of the continental shelf of Bangladesh coast compared to the other coastal region. From January to August wave average wave height is about 1meter. But during the monsoon season it becomes more than 1.5 meter due to rough weather condition. Detail about wave along Bangladesh coast is discussed in section 2.4.2. This wave controls the spreading of suspended sediment from estuary to the continental shelf. During the monsoon season due to high water discharge from the rivers with high flow velocity, suspended sediments can somewhat exceeds the

opposite force exerted by waves and reach to about 10 meter depth contour line. In the estuary the suspended sediment concentration remains very high in all season due to this wave induced bottom sediment resuspension. In the western coast the suspended sediment is comparatively low as there is high depth of continental shelf with little wave activity that could resuspend the bottom sediment with floating sediment.

Tide: Tide is another important oceanographic factor that controls the dispersal pattern of suspended sediment near shore. Tide is generally created due to the gravitational attraction of sun and moon. It is the changing form of general wave due to combine effect of reflection, coriolis force, gravitational force and friction. According to Gravitation law everything in the world attracts each other to itself. Therefore the sun and the moon also attract the earth. These attract are more effective to liquid than solid land mass. As moon is more near to the earth than the giant sun so mainly moon attraction is dominant for tide happening. For moon attraction ocean water swells up on the earth portion of the moon side. At that time the opposite portion of the earth also swells up due to coriolis force and two of the other side face falling of water. These rising and falling happen periodically in a day as the moon rotates the earth in 24 hours 50 minutes. Generally there are two rise and fall in a day so tide happen two times in a day. During rotation when the moon and the sun act together on one side then the crest or bulges become highest and the trough also lowest. This is called spring tide and this happens during new moon and full moon. During half moon, the sun and the moon attract at right angle on the earth so the moon attraction minimizes by the sun and there is little rise and fall of ocean water correspond to general tide level. This is called neap tide. Along Bangladesh coast the type of tide is semidiurnal consisting of two high tides and two low tides in 24 hours. During high tide, water swells and exerts entrainment force on the ground sediments. Where continental shelf is shallow particularly in the central coast the bottom sediments are entrained and suspended in water increasing their concentration in the suspension. Due to this force fine size particle are mainly mixed with the water. That's why in the Meghna estuary the suspended sediment concentration remains always high compared to the main channel.

3.3.2. Ocean Current

Ocean current plays a significant role in the distribution and movement of suspended sediment. They primarily control the direction of suspended sediment movement over the shelf region. During the period of May to September sediment movement is comparatively low towards the western coast due to clockwise flow of water circulation controlled by the south westerly monsoon wind. But in the post monsoon period water circulation changes its direction to counterclockwise and sediment movement occurs mostly towards the western coast due to north easterly wind. Detail about ocean current is already discussed in section 2.5.4.

3.3.3. Salinity

Salinity of water is referred to the presence of soluble salt materials in water. They come from weathering and erosional process of salt consisting minerals and are mixed with water through fluvial process. In sediment dispersion this surface salinity of sea water plays an important role. In high salinity condition suspended sediments are

Figure 18: Average Salinity Pattern of Five Stations of Three Different Years along the Coastal Belt of Bangladesh

Data source: BIWTA

flocculated and are settled due to their increased weight. In Bay of Bengal, during the monsoon period enormous fresh water discharge pushes the salt wedge back towards the sea from the estuary. Due to the dilution of huge fresh water in this season,

salinity decreases significantly up to the depth of 10 meter contour line from the shore. As a result sediments are dispersed to that extent during this season. But in the pre or post monsoon period the fluvial input is decreased from the rivers to the sea and thereby salt water wedge reaches towards the shore by pushing the fresh water input. As a result most of the suspended sediments are settled near the shore within depth of 5 meter contour line. Salinity variation between high and low tide period is not very significant (Figure 18) along the coast.

3.4. Methods and Techniques

For suspended sediment concentration estimation five sample points were selected for each location. Detail about the location of sample points are illustrated in chapter-2. Water samples were collected from each point at three different depths with a water sampler. Temperature and Salinity was recorded with alcoholic thermometer and salinity meter for each water sample. pH was also recorded with a pH meter. In laboratory, collected water samples were filtered thoroughly with filter paper. After going through measuring process the concentration of suspended sediments for each sample points at different depths were obtained. Particle density of sediment was also measured using psychomotor method.

3.5. Calculation of Suspended Sediment Concentration

For calculation of suspended sediment concentration in water, 1 liter of water sample was taken and filtered for each study point at their varying depths. After completing the filtration process of all water samples, eq-1 was used to obtain the concentration of suspended sediment in 1 liter of water.

$$SSC \text{ (gm/l)} = W_1 - W_2 \dots\dots\dots (eq-1)$$

Where,

W_1 = Weight of filter paper including filtered sediment at 80° C temperature (gm)

W_2 = Weight of empty filter paper at 80° C temperature (gm)

Salinity and pH were also tested in the laboratory to check the field data. Overall data obtained in the laboratory and from field are given in the following tables (

Table 4, Table 3).

From careful analysis it is seen that SSC is comparatively high in the Nijhum Dwip study area. SSC in both surface and bottom layer exceeds 1gm/l in this study area, but in Kuakata study area it is below 1gm/l during the study period. SSC in bottom layer for the both study areas are comparatively high than the surface and middle layer.

Table 3: SSC, Salinity, Temperature and pH Data of Nijhum Dwip Study Area (May5, 2012)

Sample Point	Sample No	Depth(m) from Water Surface	Concentration Of SSC(gm/l)	pH	Temp(°C)	Salinity (ppt)
1	Surface-1	0	1.33	7.75	30	3.7
	Middle-1	1	1.41	7.84	29.9	4.1
	Bottom-1	2	2.2	7.91	29.8	4.3
2	Surface-2	0	1.52	7.88	30	4.3
	Middle-2	0.5	2.09	7.87	29.6	4.4
	Bottom-2	1	2.23	7.86	29.5	4.4
3	Surface-3	0	1.44	7.73	30	4.3
	Middle-3	0.5	1.47	7.92	29.8	4.5
	Bottom-3	1	2.44	7.91	29.8	4.5
4	Surface-4	0	1.75	7.41	30	4.1
	Middle-4	1	2.31	7.52	29.8	4.3
	Bottom-4	1.8	3.33	7.9	29.8	4.3
5	Surface-5	0	1.32	6.97	29.9	4.1
	Middle-5	1	1.59	7.1	29.8	4.2
	Bottom-5	2	3.17	7.75	29.8	4.2

Source: Field Work, 2012

Table 4: SSC, Salinity, Temperature and pH Data of Koakata Study Area (May7, 2012)

Sample Point	Sample No	Depth(m) from Water Surface	Concentration of SSC (gm/l)	pH	Temp(°C)	Salinity(ppt)
1	Surface-1	0	0.34	7.99	30	7.4
	Middle-1	3	0.39	7.87	29.9	7.6
	Bottom-1	5	0.93	7.46	29.9	7.6
2	Surface-2	0	0.30	7.9	30	7.4
	Middle-2	2	0.32	7.69	29.8	7.4
	Bottom-2	3.88	0.47	6.72	29.8	7.5
3	Surface-3	0	0.29	7.95	30	7.7
	Middle-3	1	0.49	7.66	29.8	7.8
	Bottom-3	2	0.72	7.8	29.8	7.8
4	Surface-4	0	0.18	7.94	30	7.7
	Middle-4	2	0.20	7.41	29.8	7.7
	Bottom-4	3	0.23	7.64	29.7	7.8
5	Surface-5	0	0.09	7.92	29.9	7.3
	Middle-5	1	0.39	7.9	29.8	7.3
	Bottom-5	2.70	0.48	7.64	29.7	7.4

Source: Field Work, 2012

This is caused due to the bottom sediment resuspension owing to wave, tide and current action. Shallow continental shelf is another significant cause for this resuspension. In bottom layer SSC is high in Nijhum Dwip study area mainly due to shallow water depth and wave action. In Kuakata study area the water depth is comparatively high and this could hardly allow the bottom sediment to resuspended in water. But during high wave action, bottom sediment resuspension induced SSC may increase in this study area.

3.5.1. Vertical Change

While analyzing the vertical sediment concentration variation for each point of two study sites it is found that sediment concentration significantly increases vertically from the upper to the bottom layer. This situation largely occurs due to the uplifting and mixing of bottom sediment. These are mainly the fine grained soil particles are deposited on the shelf surface. Due to the shallow depth of the shelf these sediments are remixed in the above water under the influence of wave and tide. SSC in the bottom layer is comparatively high in the sample points of Nijhum Dwip between the two study sites. In the samples of Nijhum Dwip SSC in the Bottom layer is always

above 2gm/l which is less than 1gm/l in the samples of Kuakata. It should be noted that the depth of continental shelf is high in the Kuakata than in Nijhum Dwip. Linear curve for each study points shows a continuous increase of SSC from surface to the bottom layer. Figure 19 shows the vertical sediment fluctuation for the five sample points for two study sites.

Figure 19: Vertical Sediment Fluctuation in Study Sites. a,b,c,d and f are the illustrations of sample points 1,2,3,4,and 5 of Study site Kuakata and g, h, i, j and k are the illustrations of sample points 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 of Nijhum Dwip

Source: Field work, 2012

Source: Field work, 2012

3.5.2. Horizontal Change

From field data analysis it is found there is a spatial variation of SSC from one study point to another study point. Maximum SSC is found at the river mouth and it decreases towards in front of the main land. This occurs due to the sediment input from the river towards the mouth. In Kuakata study area Maximum SSC (0.34) for surface layer is found at sample point 1 as it is directly at the river mouth. From that point SSC decreases towards the east and at the study point 5 minimum SSC (0.09) is

found in the surface layer. For the middle layer that is at 3 meter depth from water surface maximum SSC (0.49gm/l) is found between 3 to 4 km distance from the sample point 1 towards east. But at the starting and ending point SSC is comparatively low (0.18-0.06 gm/l) in this layer due to high above from the bottom. The cause of maximum SSC fluctuation in between 3 to 4 km distance (point3) is the shallow depth of the shelf surface. Due to this shallow depth bottom sediment is easily resuspended in above water by wave and tidal action. At the Bottom layer that is almost close to the surface SSC is high for point 1, 3 and 5. The amount of SSC in this layer is significantly high compared to the surface and middle layer. The major cause is the bottom sediment mixing (Figure 20: k, l and m). In Nijhum Dwip, SSC in point 1 and point 5 are comparatively low than that of the point 2, 3 and 4 for all three layers (Figure 20: n, o and p). This is because locations of point2, 3 and 4 are shallow compared to the point 1 and point5. These points (1, 5) are located on the main channel. It is very interesting that in Kuakata study area the linear curves for all three layers show a continuous decreasing of SSC from point 1 to point 5. But in Nijhum Dwip the linear curves for all those layers show a slight increasing of SSC from point 1 to point 5. The major cause for this variation is identified as the presence of river that supplies huge suspended sediment. In Kuakata, SSC decreases towards the eastern sampling points because of the long distance from the main channel. But in point 1 it shows high SSC due to its location at the main channel. In Nijhum dwip SSC increases towards the eastern study points because of the presence of main channel of Lower Meghna River at little distance that provides ample of sediment annually.

Figure 20: Spatial Variation of SSC from Study Point 1 to Study Point 5. k(surface layer), l(middle layer) and m(bottom layer) are the illustration of Kuakata study area and n(surface layer), o(middle layer) and p(bottom layer) are the illustration of Nijhum Dwip study area.

Source: Field work, 2012

Source: Field work, 2012

3.6. Salinity, Temperature and pH in the Study Area

Salinity, pH and water temperature data were collected from field for each sample point to find out the spatial its spatial variation. To find out their vertical variation data were recorded from each layer (surface, middle, and bottom). Detail about their horizontal and vertical variation is discussed below.

3.6.1. Salinity Variation

Horizontal distribution: In every layer of water sample for each station salinity is found high in the between sample point 2 and sample point 4 at Kuakata study area. In this region salinity is high because of less influence of fresh water input. But in the locations of sample point 1 and sample point 2 salinity is low because of the fresh water dilution from the river input (, 2012

Figure 22).

Vertical distribution: In vertical layers salinity is increased from the top to bottom layer. As fresh water density is comparatively lower than the saline water, it remains on the top layers and in the bottom layers saline water intensity remains high. In Both Kuakata and Nijhum Dwip study area the picture is almost same (Figure 21). Both of Kuakata and Nijhum Dwip show comparatively high salinity in front of the main land. Due to high fresh water input in Nijhum Dwip salinity is almost half relative to Kuakata study area. A comparative picture of salinity for two study areas at different depth is illustrated in (Figure 23).

Figure 21: Vertical Salinity Variation in Kuakata(a) and Nijhum Dwip(b)

Source: Field work, 2012

Source: Field work, 2012

Figure 22: Horizontal Salinity Variation in Kuakata (a-surface layer, b-middle layer and c-bottom layer) and Nijhum Dwip (d-surface layer, e-middle layer and f-bottom layer).

Source: Field work, 2012

Source: Field work, 2012

Figure 23: Comparative Illustration of Salinity for Two Study Areas

Source: Field work, 2012

3.6.2. Temperature Variation

Horizontal change: Temperature does not show significant variation in two study areas. It is almost similar for both study areas. On the surface layer it is 30°C for 1, 2, 3, and 4 number sample points. Only 0.1°C decreases to the sample point 5. In the middle layer temperature decreases up to 0.2°C although at sample point 2 it decreases up to 0.6 to 0.5°C for both study areas. In bottom layer it is found to be highest 29.9°C at sample point 1 for both stations and for other stations it decreases up to 0.5°C (Figure 24).

Vertical change: At each sample point location temperature decreases from upper to bottom layer. In Kuakata surface temperature at point 1, 2 and 3 are same (30°C). But in point 5 it is 29.9°C. In middle layer maximum temperature is found in point 1 (29.9°C) and minimum is found in point 2, 3, 4 (29.8°C). The bottom layer temperature is also high in point 1 (29.9°C) and lowest is found in point 5 about 29.5°C (Figure 25). The surface layer of Nijhum Dwip also shows the same temperature as like as Kuakata study area. For other sample point's temperature variation is almost similar to the sample points of Kuakata. A comparative picture of temperature variation in two study areas is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 24: Horizontal Temperature Variation for at Each Layer of Kuakata (a-surface, b-middle, c-bottom layer) and Nijhum Dwip (d-surface, e-middle and f-bottom layer)

Source: Field work, 2012

Source: Field work, 2012

Figure 25: Vertical Temperature Variation at Kuakata Study Area(g) and Nijhum Dwip Study Area(h)

Source: Field work, 2012

Source: Field work, 2012

Figure 26: Comparative Illustration of Salinity for Two Study Areas

Source: Field work, 2012

3.6.3. pH Variation

Horizontal variation: pH is the negative logarithm of Hydrogen Ion concentration. For both study areas pH variation is about 6.5 to 8. Except point 5 pH decreases from surface to bottom layer (Figure 27).

Vertical variation: There is no significant difference from upper to bottom layer at each sampling point at Kuakata study area. But in Nijhum Dwip Study area it tends to decrease from surface to bottom layer at points 1, 2, and 5. But in sampling points 3 and 4, pH decreases from surface to middle layer and then increases towards the bottom layer (Figure 28).

A comparative picture of pH change for both study area is illustrated in Figure 28.

Figure 27: Horizontal pH Variation at Each Layer of Kuakata (a-surface, b-middle, c-bottom layer) and Nijhum Dwip (d-surface, e-middle and f-bottom layer)

Source: Field work, 2012

Source: Field work, 2012

Figure 28: Comparative Illustration of pH for Two Study Areas

Source: Field work, 2012

3.7. Conclusion

Suspended sediment concentration in the study areas are mainly influenced by the fresh water input from the rivers and wave action. As a result in the surface layer, maximum suspended sediment is found at the mouth of channel and it decreases in front of the main land. But in the bottom layer, for both study areas suspended sediment concentration is very high even compared to the surface layer. Salinity shows the opposite result for both study areas. In the surface layer salinity is low due the high intensity of fresh water and in the bottom layer salinity is due to high intensity of saline water as saline water density is high than the fresh water density. Temperature variation is not significant. It only varies 0.1 to 0.5°C from surface to bottom layer. pH value decreases from surface to the bottom layer for Kuakata study site but is shows a opposite result for the Nijhum Dwip study area.

**Chapter Four: Calculation of Suspended Sediment Concentration
and Dispersal Using Remote-Sensing**

4.1. Overview on Remote-Sensing

Remote-sensing is the science and art of acquisition of information about an object, area or phenomenon without touching it physically. In geographical research sometimes it becomes very essential to study in the remote area or geographically and politically inaccessible area where it is very difficult to collect information physically. Here it is undoubtedly necessary to collect remotely sensed information. For historical analysis of any event there is no alternative of Remote-sensing technique. Now a day's Remote-sensing has been used widely not only in the field of Geography but also in engineering and scientific research. To obtain information it requires mechanical instrument that is commonly called the sensor mounted on a particular platform. That platform may be an airplane, gaseous balloon or satellite. In the past the sensor was used to mount on airplane or gaseous balloon. Modern remote sensing began in 1858 when Gaspard-Felix Tournachon first took aerial photographs of Paris from a hot air balloon. The history of Remote-sensing changed on October 4, 1957, when the Soviet Union successfully launched Sputnik I, the first earth orbiting satellite. On January 31, 1958, the United States successfully launched Explorer I, another earth orbiting satellite which was capable of recording earth's magnetic field's data. These all were not capable of providing continuous information. In the late 20th century due to a rapid advance of science satellites were completely developed and are still used today to gain information on a global scale and even information about other planets in the solar system. For continuous information acquisition multi-spectral platforms such as Landsat series have been in use since the 70's. These thematic mappers take images in multiple wavelengths of electromagnetic radiation and are used for various purposes. Today's remote sensing imaging includes infra-red, aerial photographs, Hyper spectral, Doppler radar and most recently LIDAR.

The heart of Remote-sensing is the EMR that consists of solar radiation (energy) of a range of different wavelengths. In Remote-sensing the information is obtained based on the process involves the incident of radiation on a particular object and the radiation reflected by that object. Sensors capture that reflected energy as numerical code that is commonly called the DN. The values of DN vary based on the intensity of

reflection of objects. Since the intensity and wavelengths of this radiation are a function of the surface in question, each surface is described as processing a characteristic "Spectral Signature". If an instrument can identify and distinguish between different spectral signatures, then it will be possible to map the extent of surfaces using remote sensing.

The generalized processes and elements involved in electromagnetic remote sensing are represented in schematically in Figure 29. There are two different types of sensor: active sensors and passive sensors. Active sensors are those that are capable to obtain information even in the absence of sunlight. On the other hand passive sensors are totally depended on the solar energy for capturing information. Each Sensor includes some channels or bands in which the information is recorded. These bands are categorized based on the radiation wavelength and types of resolution. There are commonly four types of resolution: spectral resolution, spatial resolution, temporal resolution and radiometric resolution.

Figure 29: Process of Remote Sensing Data Acquisition and Analysis

Source: Lillesand, T.M. and Kiefer, 2002.

Remote sensing technology in recent years has proved to be of great importance in acquiring data for effective resources management and hence could also be applied to coastal environment monitoring and management. Satellite remote sensing is widely used as a tool in many parts of the world for the management of the resources and

activities within the continental shelf containing reefs, islands, mangroves, shoals, nutrient rich waters and turbid waters associated with major estuaries.

4.2. Application of Remote-Sensing in Coastal Study

Remote sensing data from satellite sensors, aerial photography and LIDAR for coastal management has been highly effective in acquiring information for marine habitat mapping, water quality monitoring, Suspended sediment concentration measurement, emergencies of new lands, environmental impact, tide monitoring, and mapping of reclamation activities for many years. The coastal zone provides resources for human and natural populations, unique ecosystems, and a range of economic activities. The carrying capacity of the coastal zone, effects from human impacts, alternations of food webs, and the mitigation of natural and anthropogenic hazards are of vital importance to a country.

Satellite images from high resolution satellite sensors and moderate resolution sensors can provide researchers and scientists with data for assessment and analysis water temperature, salinity, phytoplankton, hydrology, shoreline changes, bathymetry, soil moisture and potential threats to our coasts. Assessments and predictive capabilities through satellite imagery from satellite sensors incorporated with GIS mapping are needed to predict onset of events that may significantly affect human health, critical coastal wetlands and ecosystems, and economic development.

4.3. Application of Remote-Sensing in Suspended Sediment Dispersal and Concentration Estimation

Collecting information about Suspended Sediment Dispersal and Concentration, in coastal Waters and estuaries are vital for proper management of coastal environments. The suspension, transport, and deposition of sediment rank among the most important geomorphic processes in shaping the physical landscape (Knighton, 1998). They are particularly critical in floodplain and deltaic environments, where most landscape features are formed by the movement of sediment and water (Gomez *et. al.* 1995). Therefore, observation of spatial and temporal patterns in sediment transport is helpful in understanding the formation and function of these environments and how they may respond to natural and anthropogenic perturbations in the future. Nowadays,

in the estuarine and coastal waters (e.g., Stumpf, 1988) and in the assessment of plume variability of the large rivers (e.g., plume study in the Mississippi River, Walker, 1996) the use of satellite imagery has already been accepted in synoptic observations of sediment movement and distribution. Williams and Grabau (1973) used Remote-sensing technology for getting out the spatial distribution of suspended sediment concentration in the Chesapeake Bay in early 1973. Islam *et.al.* (2001) used satellite imagery in the distribution of suspended sediment in the coastal sea off the Ganges–Brahmaputra River mouth. This work is considered as the pioneer work for the measurement of suspended sediment concentration using remote-sensing technology (application of satellite imagery) in the coastal sea of Bangladesh. Different types of Satellite imagery and different techniques were used in the above mentioned work. Overall techniques that have been used in the suspended sediment concentration can be categorized in four general groups: (1) simple regression (correlation between single band and in-situ measurements)[e.g., Williams and Grabau (1973)], (2) spectral mixing techniques [e.g., Gomez *et. al.* 1997], (3) Band ratio technique using two and more bands [e.g., Lathrop ,1992; Populus *et. al.* 1995; Wang *et al.* 2000], and (4) multiple regressions (using multiple bands and in-situ measurements)[e.g., Binding *et. al.* 2005]. In this research work simple regression (correlation between single band and in-situ measurements) technique is used that is described elaborately in the next section (4.4).

4.4. Remote-Sensing Data and Methods Used in This Study

Traditionally, SSC used to be measured by time consuming and costly point measurements. This Method allows to accurately measuring SSC only for a point in space and time. Remote sensing from air-borne and space-borne sensors have proved to be a useful technique to such studies as it provides an instantaneous and synoptic view of sediments that would otherwise be unavailable. As remote-sensing imagery covers larger area with varying days, months and years it has become the easiest, time saving and financially economic way for the estimation of suspended sediment concentration in rivers, continental shelf, and estuary and in other dynamic water bodies. It is especially useful in large, remote or complex hydrologic environments where in situ monitoring is insufficient or impractical. Most techniques for remote

sensing of SSC construct empirical relationships between reflectance and in situ measurements collected simultaneously in the field (Curran and Novo, 1988; Schmugge *et. al.* 2002). These relationships generally take the form of a linear, logarithmic, power or exponential regression equation (Curran and Novo, 1988; Schmugge *et. al.* 2002; Topliss *et. al.* 1990), though recent work suggests that a neural network approach can improve on these basic statistical relationships (Keiner and Yah, 1998; Wang *et. al.* 2008). In addition, spectral mixture analysis has been successfully used to map SSC. Sensitivity to SSC variations is generally highest in the red portion of the spectrum (620–740 nm) (Schiebe *et. al.* 1992). While the high sensitivity of the visible portion of the spectrum, especially red, to variations in SSC is well documented, portions of the near-infrared spectrum are also sensitive to SSC alone to assess variations in turbidity or SSC (Wass *et. al.* 1997; Sterckx *et. al.* 2007) and have the advantage of being less influenced by bottom reflectance in shallow water environments than do shorter wavelengths (Tolk *et. al.* 2000). As a result, several studies have successfully utilized near-infrared reflectance though a combination of several visible and near-infrared bands often produces the most robust SSC-reflectance relationships (Stumpf and Pennock, 1989). Reflectance- SSC regressions are generally highly effective and the highest coefficient value (often $R^2 > 0.8$) have been successfully used to remotely estimate SSC in a wide variety of fluvial and oceanic environments. Ritchie *et. al.* (1976) using in situ studies concluded that wavelengths between 700 and 800 nm were most useful for determining suspended sediments in surface waters.

In this study Remote-sensing technology is used to find out the spatial distribution of suspended sediment concentration in the coastal sea of Bay of Bengal. Inspired from the NDVI technique an index (NDSSI) is used to reach a logical estimation of SSC. Landsat series of Thematic mapper sensor have been providing continuous imagery since 1970. In April 15, 1999 Landsat 7 platform was launched with the ETM+ sensor that was set in a polar, sun-synchronous orbit with a repeated coverage interval of 16 days (233 orbits). It differs from the previous sensors with a panchromatic band with 15m (49ft) spatial resolution (band 8). But On May 31, 2003 the Scan Line Corrector (SLC) in the ETM+ instrument failed. As a result the imagery after 2003 providing by

this sensor includes periodic line dropout. However, the Landsat imagery is quite perfect in the use of water quality monitoring.

In this work Landsat 7 ETM+ imagery is used and acquired for two different years. The date of acquisition and associated features are given in Table 6. Band information of imagery that is used in this work is given in Table 5.

Table 5: Landsat 7 ETM+ Band Information

Band/Channel Number	Band/Channel name	Spectral Wave Length(micrometer)	Range/ Spatial Resolution(m)
1	Blue	0.45 to 0.515	30
2	Green	0.525 to 0.605	30
3	Red	0.63 to 0.690	30
4	Near Infra-red	0.75 to 0.90	30
5	Infra-red	1.55 to 1.75	30
6	Thermal Infra-red	10.40 to 12.5	60
7	Near Infra-red	2.08 to 2.35	30
8	Panchromatic	0.52 to 0.90	15

Source: Landsat 7 Handbook

Table 6: Image Information

Image ID	Sensor	Path	Row	Date of Acquisition
LE71360452011130PFS00	ETM+	136	45	May 01,2011
LE71360452012133PFS00	ETM+	135	45	May 5,2012

Source: Landsat 7 ETM+ imagery, USGS Earth Explorer

Usually when suspended sediment concentrations are high, the backscatter/reflectivity of water are high. There are three matters dominate the reflectance of water, which are yellow substance, suspended sediment and phytoplankton. Yellow substance is a soluble matter, which has no scatter capability, but it has a strong absorption effect on short-wave bands that highly reduce the underwater downwelling irradiance. Therefore, when the absorption of water itself and yellow substance is small, actual suspended sediment information could be obtained (Wang *et. al.* 2003). To reduce the backscatter effect it is necessary to correct the image radiometrically. As the phytoplankton concentration is low (~3.0 mg/l) in the Bay of Bengal (Figure 31) it is excluded in consideration while estimation of SSC in this work.

To remove Scan line error spatial enhancement was done that was included the methods of focal analysis. For radiometric enhancement of the imagery noise and haze were reduced at the minimum level. After that atmospheric correction was done. In this stage of image processing turbid water emissivity (ϵ) was calculated. The DN values were converted to at sensor spectral radiance using the USGS equation (eq-2).

$$L_{\lambda} = \left(\frac{L_{MAX\lambda} - L_{MIN\lambda}}{Q_{cal\ max} - Q_{cal\ min}} \right) * (Q_{cal} - Q_{cal\ min}) + L_{MIN\lambda} \dots \dots \dots (eq - 2)$$

Where:

L_{λ} = the cell value as radiance

Q_{cal} = Quantized Calibrated pixel value (DN)

$L_{MIN\lambda}$ = Spectral at-sensor radiance that is scaled to $Q_{cal\ min}$ [$W/(m^2\ sr\ \mu m)$]

$L_{MAX\lambda}$ = Spectral at-sensor radiance that is scaled to $Q_{cal\ max}$ [$W/(m^2\ sr\ \mu m)$]

$Q_{cal\ min}$ = the minimum quantized calibrated pixel value (typically = 1)

$Q_{cal\ max}$ = the maximum quantized calibrated pixel value (typically = 255)

Then the radiance of each pixel was converted into TOA reflectance using the NASA equation (eq-3).

$$\rho_{\lambda} = \frac{\pi * L_{\lambda} * d^2}{ESUN_{\lambda} * \cos\theta} \dots \dots \dots (eq - 3)$$

Where:

L_{λ} = the cell value as radiance [$W/(m^2\ sr\ \mu m)$]

d^2 = Earth-Sun distance in astronomical unit

$ESUN_{\lambda}$ = Exoatmospheric Irradiance [$W/(m^2\ \mu m)$]

θ =Solar Zenith angle (degree) and π = is equal to 3.14156(unit less)

Overall methodology is illustrated in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Methodology of Remote Sensing Image Processing for SSC Estimation

It has been observed for Landsat TM/ETM imagery that Band 1 (Blue band/~ 0.450-0.515 microns) and Band 4 (Near-infrared/~0.750-0.900 microns) are most sensitive to water and water transparency (turbidity). Band 1 and Band 4 usually gives the highest and lowest reflectance values respectively for water. These characteristics have been observed for water with different levels of turbidity (Figure 32, Figure 33). Based on this principle the NDSSI is calculated (Source: *Satellite Image analysis*

Figure 34 and Figure 35) to getting out the spatial variation of SSC in the study area. This index is calculated using the eq-4. Like NDVI the values of NDSSI also range from -1 to +1 where higher values indicate the presence of more clear water and lower values indicate the presence of more turbid water or land.

$$NDSSI = \frac{B1 - B4}{B1 + B4} \dots \dots \dots (eq - 4)$$

Where, B1, and B4 are the reflectance values of Landsat 7 ETM+ Band1 (Blue) and Band 4 (Near Infra-red) respectively.

Figure 31: Average Chlorophyll Concentration in Bay of Bengal. Near the shore the concentration is high and it decreases with the distance from the shore towards the open sea. Maximum phytoplanktons are concentrated in the Meghna estuary which is brackish water environment supportive to the survival of various phytoplanktons. Ocean current may be another factor for their high concentration in this zone compared to the western coast.

Data Source: NOAA, 2011

Figure 32: Location of Spectral Profile (a) and the Spectral Profiles of Water at Different Levels of Suspended Sediment (SS) Concentrations (b). In Figure (b) the Blue band (B1) shows the highest reflectance and the Near Infra-red band (B4) shows the lowest reflectance in each profile location. Profile: 1 and Profile: 5 show the highest and lowest reflectance for both B1 and B2 respectively.

Source: Satellite Image analysis

Figure 33: Location of Spectral Profile (c) and the Spectral Profiles of Water at Different Levels of Suspended Sediment (SS) Concentrations (d). In Figure (d) the Blue band (B1) shows the highest reflectance and the Near Infra-red band (B4) shows the lowest reflectance in each profile location. Profile: 1 and Profile: 5 show the highest and lowest reflectance for both B1 and B2 respectively.

Source: Satellite Image analysis

Figure 34: NDSSI Image for May 05, 2012

Source: Satellite Image analysis

Figure 35: NDSSI Image for May 01, 2011

Source: Satellite Image analysis

After calculation of the NDSSI the in-situ SSC data is correlated with the NDSSI value to obtain the SSC for the Bangladesh coast of Bay of Bengal. In this stage the Simple Linear Regression analysis (Figure 36) is done because it shows the highest correlation coefficient (R^2) value among Power, Polynomial, Logarithmic and Linear Trend curve. The highest R^2 value indicates the highest correlation of NDSSI value

with in situ data. The algorithm used to obtain the SSC value from the NDSSI is as below-

$$SSC \text{ (gm/l)} = m \cdot NDSSI + n \quad \text{where } m \text{ and } n \text{ are the regression coefficient.}$$

The Algorithms used for two different images in this research in order to get the SSC values are as below-

$$SSC \text{ (gm/l)} = -6.614 \cdot NDSSI + 2.317 \dots \dots \dots \text{eq-4}$$

$$SSC \text{ (gm/l)} = -2.088 \cdot NDSSI + 1.591 \dots \dots \dots \text{eq-5}$$

Equation-4 is used for the May 5, 2012 image and equation-5 is used for the May 11, 2011 image.

Figure 36: Simple Linear Regression Analysis between NDSSI Value and In-situ SSC (mg/l). (a) Regression analysis for Nijhum Dwip and (b) for Kuakata

Source: Satellite Image analysis

Source: Satellite Image analysis

4.5. Spatial Distribution of Suspended Sediment Concentration in Bay of Bengal

Every year huge volume of sediment is drained by the GBM system to the coastal sea of Bay of Bengal. According to Tarafder (1975) cited in Islam (2001) 2.4 billion tons of sediment of the combined GBM river system is flowing to the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal annually through the Meghna River mouth. This huge volume of sediment is not uniformly distributed over the continental shelf. Different climatic and oceanographic factors act as driving forces in their spatial distribution. Among these, fresh water discharge from rivers and from their numerous distributaries, flow velocity of freshwater input, seasonal pattern of ocean current, Salinity fluctuation of the coastal sea, daily and monthly fluctuation of tide, wave and atmospheric disturbance as cyclone, tsunami etc are highly remarkable. From the SSC images of May month, 2011 and 2012 (Figure 38 and Figure 39) it is clear that the high turbidity zone is near the shore and it decreases from the shore to the inner sea. Highest sediment concentration zone is found in the Meghna estuary and towards the western coast it is mainly concentrated near the shoreline. This highest turbidity is mainly occurred due to the huge sediment input from the rivers as well a ground sediment re-suspension. The ground sediment re-suspension is high near the shore due to the low depth of the continental shelf. Maximum suspended sediment is found within the 5m

contour line and decreases significantly beyond to the 5m contour line but still found within the 10m contour line. If we put our eye on the whole coastal belt we see the highest suspended sediment concentration (>1 gm/l) zone is located in the central coastal part because of the high fluvial input through the Meghna river mouth. In the western coast maximum suspended sediment concentration is found (0.3-0.34 gm/l) in the rivers mouth extending up to the 6.5 km from the Kuakata sea beach, Patuakhali. In this western coast minimum suspended sediment is found that is about 0.24 gm/l. In the central coastal zone maximum suspended sediment is found up to 18km seaward from the shore of Nijhum Dwip, Noakhali. In this zone the lowest concentration is almost higher than the moderate concentration of the western coastal zone. In the eastern coast the highest concentration zone is concentrated near the Karnafully River mouth and along the shoreline. Ground sediment re-suspension is highly responsible for this high concentration in this zone. Tide is mainly responsible for this ground sediment resuspension. In the Meghna estuary tidal-induced resuspension of the bottom sediments was also concluded by Barua (1990).

Figure 37: Average Monthly Sediment and Water Discharge from the GBM System to the Coastal Sea of Bay of Bengal

Source: Coleman, 1969

During the monsoon period the sediment discharge increases significantly as well as the fresh water input (Figure 37). As the flow velocity of fresh water remains highest in this period it pushes the salt wedge far away from the coast. During this time maximum suspended sediment concentration may be higher than 2gm/l and the zone of maximum turbidity may exceed the 5m contour line.

Figure 38: Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC) Map on May 1, 2011 in the Western Bangladesh Coast of Bay of Bengal.

Source: Satellite Image analysis

Figure 39: Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC) Map on May 1, 2011 in the Eastern Bangladesh Coast of Bay of Bengal.

Source: Satellite Image analysis

4.6. Impact of Sea Surface Temperature and Salinity on Suspended Sediment Concentration Variation

Sea surface salinity (SSS) and sea surface temperature (SST) are major controlling factors in the distribution of suspended sediment concentration where bottom sediment re-suspension is low. Salinity leads to the suspended clay particles to be flocculated to each other. As a result the mass of the suspended clay particles increases. Due to this mechanism the settling velocity of the sediment increases and in water their concentration decreases. From chapter-3 we see that there is a good

relationship between the SST and SSL. In near coast the SSL concentration is slightly depended upon the SST. With the increase of SST the SSL concentration slightly increases. But in this research the SSC in near shore is not influenced highly by the SST and SSL in the monsoon period. Rather than in this period it is highly influenced by the fresh water input and sediment discharge. But in the pre-monsoon and post-monsoon period the SSC is influenced by SSL and SST beyond to the 5m contour line towards the inner sea.

4.7. Conclusion

Suspended sediment concentration and its distribution is studied in this chapter. For this purpose Remote Sensing technology is applied. For understanding the distribution pattern of suspended sediment NDSSI index is used. From this index the quantitative calculation of suspended sediment estimation is done using the simple linear regression analysis that is correlated with the NDSSI value. From the SSC images it is concluded that the maximum turbidity zone is located near the shore within the 5m contour line. In the season of low water discharge from the river the turbidity mainly occurs due to the bottom sediment re-suspension influenced by tidal and wave energy. But during the period of high water discharge (monsoon season) the zone of turbidity exceeds the 5m contour line. SSC maps indicate that high magnitude of SSC (>1 gm/l) is in the estuary near the shore but in the channels or beyond 10m contour is not significant (<0.3 mg/l).

Chapter Five: Topographic Change of the Continental Shelf

5.1. Introduction

Bottom topography is the surface configuration of bottom of lake, river, sea or ocean. Bottom topography of a water body is not constant. It is changeable. Bottom topography of an open water body is changed due to several factors. These may include sediment deposition, erosion and tectonic activities. The method of the study of bottom topography of a water body is commonly known as bathymetric analysis. Bathymetry analysis is the underwater topography analysis of rivers, lakes, sea or ocean. Data used in bathymetric analysis are collected from echo sounder from a number of points of a water body that uses the echo of particular wavelength of sound. It is the latest technology for collecting bathymetric data. In the study of continental shelf of Bangladesh, bathymetric points are collected by Bangladesh NAVY. In this study bathymetric data charts were used from which bathymetric points were processed using Arc GIS software (version 9.3.1) for the analysis of bottom topography of the continental shelf of Bangladesh.

5.2. Characteristic of Bottom Topography of Continental Shelf

The continental shelf of Bay of Bengal of Bangladesh region is 160 km (Islam, 2001) wide where the continental slope starts at about 80m datum line (BIWTA, 1982 cited in Islam, 2001). It is a gently sloping surface from north to south with an average slope 1:800 (Islam, 2001). The outer edge of the shelf is marked by an abrupt increase in slope that is called the shelf break or shelf edge. The water depth to the shelf break varies from 20 to 500 m, but average around 130 m (Krishna, nd). There is also a very gentle slope from east to west towards the Swatch of no Ground, the most prominent feature on the Bengal shelf. Detail about the Swatch of no Ground is discussed in section 2.2. The continental shelf is shallow about less than 5m depth near the Meghna estuary. The depth of shelf in the western coast is comparatively high than the central and eastern coast. Along the eastern coast the depth of the shelf increases near the Teknaf coast.

5.3. Available Data and Techniques

For bottom topography analysis of the continental shelf of Bangladesh region bathymetric charts of BIWTA were used in this study. Two bathymetric charts were

used that were published in 1982 and 2009. Bathymetric chart published in 2009 include survey of deferent years from 2003 to 2009. Based on these survey years whole Bay of Bengal in Bangladesh region was divided into 6 grids. The large grid (Grid-6) was divided into four sub grids (6-A, 6-B, 6-c and 6-D) for detail analysis (Figure 40). Survey years of these grids and their associated information's are given in Table 7. Based on these

Figure 40: Bathymetry of Bay of Bengal (DEM) (Data-1982). A1, A2 and A3 are the location of cross profiles.

Source: Bathymetry Data Chart 1982 (BIWTA)

Survey grids, the bathymetry chart published in 2009 was also gridded for comparative analysis. The bathymetry points were than analyzed Using Arc GIS (version 9.3.1), Surfer (version 10), Micro Dem and 3Dem software packages. For cross profile analysis 2 transect lines towards north-south and east-west direction were drawn on each grid and using 3D analyst tool of Arc GIS software package every cross profile were created. For volumetric calculation of depositional and

scouring area, cut/fill method was used. Overall methodology is illustrated in Figure 41 .

Table 7: Grid Information

Grid Number	Survey Year		Relative Location of Grids	Area (sq km)
	Bathymetry Chart-01	Bathymetry Chart-02		
Grid-1	1982	2006-2007	20km west from Chittagong coast, 20 km south from Hatia	2321.19
Grid-2	1982	2008-2009	10km west from Teknaf coast	7874.48
Grid-3	1982	2004-2005	Adjoining with Feni and Chittagong coast	6718.48
Grid-4	1982	2007-2008	Adjoining with Patenga coast	355.61
Grid-5	1982	2005-2006	Adjoining with southern tip of Teknaf	791.27
Grid: 6-A	1982	2002-2004	Adjoining with Satkhira, Khulna and Patuakhali coast	5704.76
Grid: 6-B	1982	2002-2005	Adjoining with Bhola and Noakhali coast	8199.19
Grid: 6-C	1982	2002-2006	10 km south from Satkhira and 20 km south from Khulna and Patuakhali coast	18412.19
Grid: 6-D	1982	2002-2007	10 km south from Bhola, adjoining with Teknaf coast	15920.8

Source: Bathymetry Chart 1982, 2009 (BIWTA) and GIS Data Analysis

Figure 41: Illustration of Complete Methodology used for Bathymetry Analysis

5.4. Change of the Bottom Topography

To understand the change of bottom topography three different level of analysis was done. These were volumetric analysis, Time series analysis and Cross section analysis. These are described below-

5.4.1. Volumetric Analysis

In this section the area of sediment deposition and scouring by grid were identified. Their area and volume of deposited and scoured sediment were calculated using statistical method. Detail result is discussed below-

From volumetric analysis it is found that in Bay of Bengal total estimated volume of deposited sediment is about 314.634 km^3 which covers an area of 35703.66 km^2 and

total estimated volume of scoured sediment is 151.51 km^3 with an area of 20763.98 km^2 during the study period of 1982 to 2009. Maximum deposition is found in Grid: 6-C which is $2.59.573 \text{ km}^3$ with an area of 9643.53 km^2 . Maximum scouring is also found in the same grid that is 132.842 km^3 with an area of 8286.73 km^2 during the study period. Minimum deposition and scouring is found in Grid-4. Deposited region covers 0.62 km^3 with an area of 617.42 km^2 and scouring region covers 0.041 km^3 with an area of 41.33 km^2 (Figure 42). Average density of particle is about 2.66 gm/ml .

Figure 42: Grid-Wise Bottom Topography Change of the Continental Shelf of Bay of Bengal (a- indicates the 1982 bathymetry, b- indicates the bathymetry of survey year according to table7- column- 2 and c- indicates the volumetric and aerial change over these periods). A-B and C-D lines indicate cross profile lines that are discussed widely in section 5.4.3.

Source: BIWTA Data processed in Arc GIS-9.3.1(2012)

Source: BIWTA Data processed in Arc GIS-9.3.1(2012)

5.4.2. Time Series Analysis

In this section based on 1982 bottom topography change was projected to 2025 and 2050 AD. While doing this, the rate of scouring and sedimentation during the last two time periods (1982 and last survey year for each grid) for each grid was thought constant. Rate of sedimentation and scouring for each grid are already illustrated in each grid of Figure 42. During the projected years some areas may reach to the Mean Sea Level (MSL) and some areas may rise above the High Tide limit (along Bangladesh coast average Tidal level fluctuation is 1meter) about that is considered as 1meter above the MSL. From these projections it is found that within 2025AD 3355.08km² areas may reach to the MSL and 2366.11km² areas may rise above 1meter from the MSL. During this period of time maximum areas that may reach to the MSL is about 1304.08km² in Grid: 6-B and maximum 916.81km² areas may rise above 1meter from the MSL at the same grid. Grid-3, Grid: 6-A, Grid: 6-B, Grid: 6-C and Grid: 6-D may play a significant role in this case. But if the projection period is extended to 2050, about 6485.82km² area may reach to the MSL and about 5534.12 km² area may rise above 1meter from the MSL. During this projected period maximum 1304.08km² area may reach to MSL and maximum 916.81km² area may rise above the 1meter from the MSL. Both are in the Grid: 6-B. Grid: 6-A, Grid: 6-C and Grid: 6-D may also contribute to these. Grid wise projected information is given in Table 7. Areas that will reach the MSL and rise above 1meter from the MSL are shown in (Figure 43).

Figure 43: Gridwise Projected Bottom Topography. Green color indicates area that may reach MSL and red color indicates area that may rise above high water tide level. 2025 and 2050 are the extensions of projected years.

Source: BIWTA Data processed in Surfer-10 (2012)

Source: BIWTA Data processed in Surfer-10 (2012)

5.4.3. Cross Section Analysis

Cross section analysis was mainly done to see the spatial variation of Bottom topography. In this analysis two cross profile lines were drawn in each Grid (Figure 42) approximately from north to south and from east to west direction. In this analysis spatial variation of bottom topography was mainly carry out for three different time periods. 1982 bottom topographic data was used as the base and in relation to that data projected 2025 and projected 2050 data were plotted to create cross profile along east-west and north-south direction. The spatial variation of bottom topography of the continental shelf is shown in Figure 44 for different grids.

Bottom topography change in east-west direction

In Grid-1 within 5 to 17 km from point-A, there would be a place of sediment accumulation but not reach to MSL and after reaching 17km distance the area would be scoured up to point-B with slight fluctuation. In Grid-2, sediment accumulation increases significantly from point-A to point-B. But during the projected there would not be raise any land to the MSL.

Figure 44: Spatial Variation of Bottom Topography along Nearly East-West Direction. A-B profile locations for each grid are illustrated in Figure 42. Red, blue and olive colored lines indicate the bottom topography profiles for 1982, projected year 2025 and projected year 2050 respectively. PG and PL indicate the projected gain and projected loss areas from 1982 to 2025 and 2025.

Source: Time Series Analysis from BIWTA Bathymetry Data

Source: Time Series Analysis from BIWTA Bathymetry Data

In Grid-3, at the distance between 20km and 25km there is a possibility to raise bottom topography above MSL but it may not rise above 1m from MSL. In Grid-4, there is a possibility to rise bottom layer slightly at MSL between 5 to 8km distance from the point-A. Grid-5 may show a continuous rise of bottom above 1m from the MSL for both 2025 and 2050 projected period. Grid: 6-A shows a continuous undulation of bottom topography remaining below the MSL for both projected period. But at 96km distance near point-B bottom layer of the shelf may rise above the MSL for both projected period but it may not rise above 1m from the MSL. In Grid: 6-B, between 40 km distance from point-A two areas may rise at 2050 projected period but at 50 km distance from point-A there would be high scoured area. After that scouring point several lands may rise above MSL up to 0.5 meter at 2050 projected year. Profile of Grid: 6-C is across the Swatch of No Ground. From this profile it is seen that in the western edge of this canyon new lands may emerge above 1m from the MSL at 2050 projected period but in the eastern part of the canyon there may not any significant land emergence. In Grid: 6-D there will not any rise of new land for both projected period although continuous siltation may occur there.

Bottom topography change in east-west direction

Cross profile analysis does not show any significant land submergence in Grid-1, Grid-2 and Grid-5 for 2025 and 2050 projected duration. Grid-5 shows significant land scouring of the shelf from point-C to 15 km distance. In Grid-1 shelf may be continuously silted on 2025 and 2050 projected period. At the southern end of this Grid, siltation rate is high there for this part has a possibility to raise at sea MSL in far future. In Grid-3 within 10km distance from the point-C and after 35 km distance there may rise new landmass that could reach above 1m from the MSL on 2050 projected period but for 2025 projected period these may rise only 20 to 30 cm above the MSL. Grid-4 also shows a possibility of significant landmass emergence during both projected period. But on 2025AD projected period there may not any landmass that could raise high above MSL. New landmass could be found in this grid that may rise above 1m from the MSL only on the projected period 2025. In other grids there is low possibility to emerge new landmass but significant scouring of the shelf (Figure 45). In Grid: 6-C a highly scoured area may be found at 100km distance from point-C.

Figure 45: Gridwise Continental Shelf Topography Change along North-South Direction. C-D profile locations for each grid are illustrated in Figure 42. Red, blue and olive colored lines indicate the bottom topography profiles for 1982, projected year 2025 and projected year 2050 respectively. PG and PL indicate the projected gain and projected loss areas from 1982 to 2025 and 2025.

Source: Time Series Analysis from BIWTA Bathymetry Data

5.4. Source: Time Series Analysis from BIWTA Bathymetry Data

5.5. Conclusion

The bottom topography of the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal has been continuously changing. Fluvial and oceanographic processes are mainly responsible for this. On the bottom of the continental shelf a very undulating topography is seen from the cross profile analysis. The roughness of the shelf is very high near the shore because fluvial and oceanographic processes are very active in this region. As distance increases from shore to the open sea, the roughness comparatively decreases. Maximum roughness occurs near the shore due to very high action of wave, current and velocity of fresh water flow.

Chapter Six: Implication

6.1 Introduction

The success of any research work depends on its implication. Every good research work has some implication. Similarly, this research work has some implications that are discussed below.

6.2 Suspended sediment concentration and dispersion

Along the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal in Bangladesh region, maximum SSC (1.9mg/l during the study period, May 05, 2012) is found in the Meghna estuary. Sediments that are carried by the GBM River system are discharged in this region and due to wave and tidal action these can be hardly dispersed beyond the 5meter depth contour line. A significant amount of suspended sediment is deposited in this zone. As a result this zone is decreasing in its depth. In this zone there is a good possibility of the emergence of new islands.

6.3. Sub aqua sediment accumulation

The continental shelf of the Bay of Bengal along the Bangladesh coastline is comparatively shallow. In the Meghna estuary region it is shallower, around 3-5m below the water surface. In this zone tidal influence is comparatively high within the main channel. From cross profile analysis along A1 and A2 (Figure 40) it is found that the river bed is more deep than the continental shelf. The continental shelf in front of the lower Meghna River is comparatively high (Figure 46) and undulating. This is due to the high sediment deposition rate in this estuary. As a result, the continental shelf in this estuary continuously uprises. When fresh water flows from the Meghna channel it may be directly obstructed by the shallow continental shelf. Due to this obstruction the velocity of fresh water flow may be decreased. Due to this decreasing flow velocity sediment deposition rate in this zone may be very high (0.31km³/yr during 1982-2007, source- bathymetric analysis, section 5.4.1 in this study). The tidal limit in the main channel is comparatively high compared to the estuary. From this cross profile analysis it may be assumed that, when water flow from the river is obstructed by the shallow continental shelf it swells that increases the tidal limit within the channel. As a result a local tide level rise may be found within the main channel near the estuary.

Figure 46: Cross Profile along A1 and A2 According to Figure 40

Source: Cross profile analysis of BIWTA bathymetry data using Arc GIS-9.3.1.

Source: Cross profile analysis of BIWTA bathymetry data using Arc GIS-9.3.1.

Source: Cross profile analysis of BIWTA bathymetry data using Arc GIS-9.3.1.

But in the western coast the continental shelf is almost flat to the river bed that allows fresh water input to flow directly towards the open sea. In this zone sedimentation rate is comparatively low ($0.15\text{km}^3/\text{yr}$, source: bathymetric analysis-section 5.4.1 in this study). In future around 2025 and 2050 many new landmass can rise in this zone if the present sedimentation rate remains active. Location of those predicted landmasses are shown in Figure 42: Grid-3, 2025 and Grid-3, 2050.

6.4. Navigation Problem

From bathymetry data analysis it is found that the continental shelf has a gentle slope from east to west and from north to south. But the shallow depth of the shelf may cause navigation problem. If the present sedimentation rate remains constant around 2050 many new islands may be emerged on the continental shelf near shore that may cause a great navigation problem.

6.5. Coastal Disaster

If present sedimentation rate becomes active the continental shelf will be uprising in many places. As a result wave action may be destructive for the coastal islands. In general wave action is high in shallow continental shelf due to wave diffraction and wave breakings. Coastal erosion may also increase due to the increase of local tidal level within the channel near the estuary.

Finally it can be suggested for an efficient coastal management considering the concentration of suspended sediment, their dispersal and siltation characteristics.

Chapter Seven: Conclusion

7.1. Introduction

Sediment is the fundamental component of coastal landforms. Sea floor acts as a reservoir of sediment that comes from the upstream and surrounding catchment areas. These sediments are carried and deposited to the sea by fluvial process that is included erosion, transportation and finally deposition. Deposition of sediment on the sea floor is not uniform. As a result, the bottom topography of the sea floor varies spatially. The uneven distribution of sediment deposition over the sea floor is primarily driven by the variation of suspended sediment dispersal pattern. In this study the major concern was to measure the spatial variation of suspended sediment concentration and find out their dispersal pattern over the continental shelf of Bay of Bengal. During this study there were some limitations and based on those limitations some suggestions are recommended.

7.2. Major Findings

Major findings of this study have been summarized below

- i. Suspended sediment distribution over the continental shelf of Bangladesh is not uniform. Maximum suspended sediments are found in the Meghna estuary for all season. Suspended sediment concentration decreases towards the west from Meghna estuary.
- ii. In the estuary suspended sediment concentration is high even compared to the main channel. This situation mainly occurs due to the bottom sediment resuspension for shallow depth of the continental shelf.
- iii. Bottom sediments are resuspended in the above water column mainly due to the wave and tidal action.
- iv. Maximum suspended concentration is found in the bottom layer and it decreases towards the upper layer.
- v. During the study period, maximum suspended sediment is found about 1.2-1.9gm/l in the Meghna estuary and minimum is found about 0.2-0.4gm/l in the western coast near the head of Swatch of No Ground.

- vi. The topography of the continental shelf is very shallow (less than 5m) in Meghna estuary and in the western coast it is comparatively deeper about 15 to 20m deep.
- vii. Continental shelf in front of the river mouth at the Meghna estuary is comparatively high due to continuous sediment deposition. This shallow continental shelf obstructs the river flow and causes coastal erosion in Swandip, Hatia and Bhola.
- viii. The shelf topography is very undulating with a gentle slope from east to west.

7.3. Limitations

The limitations of the study are

- i. Insufficiency of proper instrument for water samples collection from different depths of water column. In general, for this type of study Niskin bottle is used that is associated with temperature, conductivity and depth sensor instrument. Due to the lacking of this instrument salinity and temperature collected by normal instrument show a little unusual fluctuation.
- ii. Tidal data that are used in this study has huge data gap. Updated data were not found.
- iii. All of the BIWTA sediment discharge and water discharge stations are located in the upstream and inland channel. There are no sediment and water discharge stations in the coastal region. As a result actual water and sediment discharge data in the coastal region could not found.
- iv. For coastal study in situ data with their spatial and temporal variations are very important. But there is no sufficient instrumental setup for coastal study. As a result the scope of the study was limited.
- v. For coastal parameter study it needs long time procedure to study and collect data in different times of the year. But due to time consistency it was not possible to collect data for different seasons of the year. That is why; the analysis of temporal variations of suspended sediment over the continental shelf is not included in this study.

- vi. Bathymetric points used in this study are mainly collected by Bangladesh NAVY. They collect these data for their own perspective. They collect data dividing Bay of Bengal into several grids. Different grids are surveyed in different years. As a result it was not possible to carry out a complete picture of the Bay of Bengal in this study.
- vii. For coastal study safety is a major concern specially while working on the sea. But there are no particular safety measures for coastal research in Bangladesh. In this study, samples were collected from the 3 to 5kms in the sea only using fishing boat that was very risky and hard to collect sample accurately.

7.4. Recommendations

Based on the above limitations of the study the following suggestions can be recommended

- i. Sediment and water discharge stations should be set up in the coastal zone for coastal research and continuous monitoring for these stations should be ensured.
- ii. There should be a coastal research institute that will help the coastal researcher with necessary instrumental support.
- iii. Enriched laboratory should be developed for coastal data processing and analysis.
- iv. An enriched satellite image database should be developed for coastal study.
- v. For continuous monitoring of the coastal parameters a geo stationary satellite should be set up immediately.
- vi. Fund should be increased in the coastal research.

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Appendices

Appendix-i: Month Sediment Discharge

Month	Water Discharge	Sediment Discharge
January	10000	4
February	9000	3
March	9000	3
April	10000	8
May	21000	18
June	40000	35
July	68000	70
August	91000	125
September	80000	110
October	40500	48
November	20000	6
December	18000	5

Appendix-ii: Solar Exo-Atmospheric Irradiance

ETM+ Solar Spectral Irradiances	
Band	watts/(meter squared * μm)
1	1969.000
2	1840.000
3	1551.000
4	1044.000
5	225.700
7	82.07
8	1368.000

Appendix-iii: Sea Salinity along Depth from Surface to Bottom Layer

Salinity(PSU)	Depth(m)
30.6811	0
31.2247	10
32.2327	20
33.0574	30
33.8768	50

34.4019	75
34.6949	100
34.8389	125
34.908	150
34.9663	200
35.0109	250
35.0241	300
35.0293	400
35.0244	500
35.0076	600
34.9932	700
34.9755	800
34.9589	900
34.9407	1000
34.9176	1100
34.8986	1200
34.8773	1300
34.8637	1400
34.8459	1500
34.7985	1750
34.7961	2000

Appendix-iv: Month Mean Salinity of Bay of Bengal

Month	Mean Salinity(PSU)
January	29.359
February	30.116
March	32.301
April	33.223
May	33.322
June	30.97

July	28.84
August	24.202
September	25.152
October	26.168
November	25.95
December	30.888

Appendix-v: Tidal Data in Five Stations along Bangladesh Coast

	Year	High Tide	Low Tide
Chardoani	2001	348.625	315.625
	2005	462.5	452.75
	2008	369.53	384.17
Char-Fession	2001	74.69	77.5
	2005	27.5	29.17
	2008	956.92	389.76
Gulbonia	2001	238.75	222.5
	2005	318.17	383.6
	2008	138.04	158.83
Patharghata	2001	447.92	368.06
	2005	536.25	547.5
	2008	2744.4	2371.275
Tajumuddin	2001	80.625	81.25
	2005	93.83	103.5
	2008	240.756	241.489

Appendix-vi: Field Work Data of Kuakata Study Area

Sample Point	Sample No	Concentration(gm/l)	pH	Field Temp(deg C)	Salinity
1	Surface-1	0.3416	7.75	30	3.7
	Middle-1	0.1845	7.84	29.9	4.1
	Bottom-1	0.936631579	7.91	29.8	4.3
2	Surface-2	0.3092	7.88	30	4.4
	Middle-2	0.319894737	7.87	29.6	3.9
	Bottom-2	0.466631579	7.86	29.5	4.4
3	Surface-3	0.2947	7.73	30	4.5
	Middle-3	0.488222222	7.92	29.8	4.3
	Bottom-3	0.716105263	7.91	29.79	4.3
4	Surface-4	0.1316	7.41	30	4.1
	Middle-4	0.203333333	7.52	29.8	4.3
	Bottom-4	0.230941176	7.9	29.5	4.3
5	Surface-5	0.0989	6.97	29.9	4.4
	Middle-5	0.061111111	7.1	29.8	4.2
	Bottom-5	0.478285714	7.75	29.7	4.1

Appendix-vii: Field Work Data of Nijhum Dwip Study Area

Sample No	Depth(m)	Distance(km)	Concentration(gm/l)	Salinity(ppt)	pH	Temp(deg C)
Surface-1	0	2.2	0.3281	7.4	7.99	30
Middle-1	3	2.2	0.4088	7.6	7.87	29.9
Bottom-1	5	2.2	2.204555556	7.6	7.46	29.9
Surface-2	0	3.2	1.5227	7.4	7.9	30
Middle-2	2	3.2	2.0902	7.4	7.69	29.8
Bottom-2	3.88	3.2	2.2323	7.5	6.72	29.8
Surface-3	0	5.2	1.437	7.7	7.95	30
Middle-3	1	5.2	1.4688	7.8	7.66	29.8
Bottom-3	2	5.2	2.4442	7.8	7.8	29.8
Surface-4	0	7.02	1.7527	7.7	7.94	30
Middle-4	2	7.02	2.3063	7.7	7.41	29.8

Bottom-4	3	7.02	3.3255	7.8	7.64	29.7
Surface-5	0	8	1.3206	7.3	7.92	29.9
Middle-5	1	8	1.5967	7.3	7.9	29.8
Bottom-5	2.7	8	3.170444444	7.4	7.64	29.7

Photos

Lab Works

Field Work: Water Sample Collection

